

TEACHING REPORT TEXT BY USING SCIENTIFIC APPROACH WITH DISCOVERY LEARNING STRATEGIES

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Abstract: Combination of discovery learning and teaching report text are suitable because will combine the process of getting the goal wanted. 1. Stimulation, Teacher stimulate students by giving picture, video or information to make them think. It is purposed to make the students wants to observe further. 2. problem statement After giving stimulation, teacher give chance to the students to identify as much as possible. 3. Collection ,When students exploring the material, teacher also give chance to the students to collect information as much as possible to prove which true or not the hypothesis. 4. Processing ,All information are processed and classified so the students are able to form a concept from the data they got. 5. Verification , In this step students verify or check all of the data carefully to prove which true or not hypothesis with alternative findings. 6. generalization , A step to make a summary that can be a general principle and acceptable in any conditions.

Key words: Report Texts, Discovery Learning, Scientific Approach

INTRODUCTION

A newly designed curriculum called as K-13 (Curriculum 2013) was officially implemented in the beginning of 2013. A scientific approach becomes the most significant part of it. Some researchers had researched about implementation of scientific approach in the classroom and they found that the implementation is not optimal (Zaim, 2017). There are many teachers who are not able to implement scientific approach perfectly, the teachers use less than five steps that actually must be implemented in the classroom. Most of teachers had difficulty in implementing scientific approach because they have a little knowledge about it.

Moreover, from the students they are not ready with new process of implementation of scientific approach (Kartikawati, 2015). Apriauny (2016) mentioned that, teaching English using scientific approach should get more attention, especially upgrading the teacher in knowledge and skill aspects. Many teachers are not able to implement scientific approach in teaching English. Wahyono (2017) also stated, the learning outcomes are low, those are influenced by teacher. Teachers' less involvement in arranging k13 and most of teacher adopted from other schools and teachers are not able to connect the learning material with student's ability and condition. Most researchers stated that applying scientific approach is not easy as thought.

Besides, the researchers above mostly concern on the implementation of scientific approach that done by teacher. Therefore, this research will also concern on the implementation of discovery learning in teaching report and students view in implementation of

scientific approach using discovery learning in teaching report to fill the gap of previous studies. Discovery is similar with scientific approach, seeing this point and consider with new variable that can be added in this research, it will give more information that will be helpful in the education further. Researcher hopes there is a difference that as useful finding on the study to be used in the next learning.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The scientific approach that used in curriculum 2013 today is adoption of scientific method (Puspita, 2016). Lake & Bryant (2006) stated that, scientific method has six steps such as, asking question, doing background research, building background research, test the hypothesis by analyzing data and sketch a conclusion then communicating the result. Based on Kemendikbud (2014) stated that, scientific approach has five processes, they are observing, questioning, experimenting, associating, and communicating. Scientific approach that applied in curriculum 2013 is coming from modification of scientific method (Puspita, 2016).

In observing process, teachers may use the real phenomenon, challenging, and attracting process, (Puspita, 2016). Hosnan (2014) the process of observing is a strategy using contextualized approach because needs media. Media that used can be real media brought in the classroom or topic that. Using real phenomenon, a challenging, and attracting process is purposed to connect regalia with the material that will be learned in the classroom. Teacher can stimulate student by showing picture or video then students observe it. The teacher tries to facilitate them to be more active, increasing their critical thinking, and stimulate to speak up. Priyana (2014) stated that, this stage teachers have some rules, such as:

1. Supporting the student to checklist items to catch comprehension and make the target text
2. Supplying checklist of the materials from which students can be decided
3. Create some materials from topic

Questioning

The next step is questioning. It is the process of building knowledge. It is used for asking about the social function of text that discussed. From this step, it's hoped to develop the curiosity and the critical thinking of the student. So that the question must be able to stimulate thinking skill of the students.

The Ministry of Education describes the activities of questioning consist of some stages such as:

1. Give Q&A section to the students
2. Give chance to the students to compose question depend on the identified material observation
3. Support students to propose temporary answer depend on the knowledge stated by Priyana (2014), teacher in this stage is the facilitator or guider to make questions.

Experimenting

The purpose of this step is to make the students feel that they have learned skill. In this step, they will practice and express what they learned using language in the real life by using simulation, dialogue, role play, discussion, presentation or playing game.

The steps following in this stage are:

1. Students will collect the fact, then they start to communicate
2. Students brows and build experimenting in order to get vocab, structure to get the communicating in the context
3. Teachers give feedback, attention, or asking the students to enrich the comprehension
4. Students orally communicating the statement

Associating

This is the process of students to develop their ability to classify and compare. The role of the teacher here as the guider. Teacher guides students to classify and compare text based on the social function, the generic structure, and language feature then connect information in the text for enriching when creating text. According to Priyana (2014), teachers’ role is helping students to know the pattern on the material. Helping students to draw conclusion.

Communicating

This is the step for students communicate what they have got in the learning process that day. Present and elaborate what students observed based on their analysis along the learning process, (Hosnan, 2014). In this step teacher will facilitate everything to make the students

more active. (Priyana, 2014) stated that, the role of teacher here is to give correction, correct and enrich students' knowledge. After all, teacher will give the correct information and conclusion based on the topic discussed. instead of a final form. In this learning model teacher has a role as guider and lets the students to be more active in the learning process.

According to Syah (2004), there 6 steps that teacher must do to apply discovery learning in the classroom:

1. Stimulation

The stimulation at this stage serves to provide the conditions for the interaction learning that can develop and assist students in exploring ingredient of learning.

2. problem statement

After stimulation, the next step is to give opportunities for students to identify as many related problem agendas as possible, then one of them is selected and formulated in the form of a hypothesis.

3. Collection

When the exploration takes place, the teacher also provides opportunities for the students to collect as much information as possible that is relevant to prove whether the hypothesis is true or not.

4. Processing

Processing is an activity to process data and information that students have obtained either through interviews, observations, and so on, and then interpreted.

5. Verification

At this stage students carry out careful checks for prove whether true or not the predetermined hypothesis with findings alternatives, linked to the results of data processing.

6. Generalization

Generalization stage is a process of drawing conclusions that can be used as general principles and apply to all events or the same problem, taking into account the results of the verification.

Discovery Learning in Teaching Report

According to (Irawan, 2015) he stated that discovery learning stimulates students to optimize their way of thinking. Discovery learning and report text become the way to reach the goal of learning. Combination of discovery learning and teaching report text are suitable because will combine the process of getting the goal wanted.

Teacher who wants to apply this method can use six steps from Syah (2004):

1. Stimulation

Teacher stimulate students by giving picture, video or information to make them think. It is purposed to make the students wants to observe further.

2. problem statement

After giving stimulation, teacher give chance to the students to identify as much as possible.

3. Collection

When students exploring the material, teacher also give chance to the students to collect information as much as possible to prove which true or not the hypothesis.

4. Processing

All information are processed and classified so the students are able to form a concept from the data they got.

5. Verification

In this step students verify or check all of the data carefully to prove which true or not hypothesis with alternative findings.

6. generalization

A step to make a summary that can be a general principle and acceptable in any conditions.

REFERENCE

Appriauny, L., Afrianto., & Nababan, M. (2016) The Implementation Of Scientific Approach In Teaching English In Senior High School Pekanbaru. https://www.academia.edu/37502822/THE_IMPLEMENTIN

**G_OF_SCIENTIFIC_APPROACH_IN_TEACHING_ENGLISH_AT_SM
PN_REJANG_LEBONG**

Kartikawati, Y. (2015) The Implementation Of Scientific Approach In Teaching English At The Eight Grade Of Smp Muhammadiyah 10 Surakarta In 2014/ 2015 Academic Year: A Naturalistic Study. Surakarta: University of Muhammadiyah Surakarta. <http://eprints.ums.ac.id/32827/13/NASKAH%20PUBLIKASI.pdf>

Wahyono. Abdulhak, I., Rusman. (2017). Implementation Of Scientific Approach Based Learning To Think High Levels In State Senior High School In Ketapang. International Journal of Education and Research Vol. 5 No. 8 August 2017 <https://www.ijern.com/journal/2017/August-2017/20.pdf>

Tristy, R., T. (2010). Improving Students' Skill In Writing Report Text With All About Animals Vcd (An Action Research At The Ninth Year Students Of Smp 2 Kudus In The Academic Year 2009/2010). <http://lib.unnes.ac.id/3090/1/6571.pdf>

Puspita, E., D. (2016). Elsp Students' Problems In Implementing Scientific Approach During Practice Teaching Program. Yogyakarta: University Sanata Dharma. <https://core.ac.uk/download/pdf/80763158.pdf>

Kemendikbud. (2014). Konsep Dan Implementasi Kurikulum 2013. <https://www.kemdikbud.go.id/kemdikbud/dokumen/Paparan/Paparan%20Wamendik.pdf>

Nuraeni, C., (2016). Improving Students' Writing Ability Report Text By Using P.I.E Strategy. December 2018 English Education English Journal for Teaching and Learning 6(2):228. <https://urlshortner.org/cmjVd>

Lake, L. W., & Bryant S. L. (2006). The Scientific Method And Earth Sciences. Digital Collection 123, 1-2.

<https://asmedigitalcollection.asme.org/energyresources/article/128/4/245/446952/The-Scientific-Method-and-Earth-Sciences>

Hosnan, M. (2014). Pendekatan Saintifik Dan Kontekstual Dalam Pembelajaran Abad 21. Bogor: Penerbit Ghalia Indonesia.

Priyana, Joko. (2014). The English Language Teaching Steps Based On The Scientific Method. A Paper Presented In A Teacher Training On The Scientific Method, In Yogyakarta State University.

Musfiqon. & Nurdyansah. (2015). Pendekatan Pembelajaran Saintifik. Book

Barawati, D. A. (2018). The Use Of Scientific Approach To Improve Students' Writing Ability. <https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/THE-WRITING-PROCESS-%3A-An-Overview-of-Research-on-as/db746c718fb3798326cb8ab87f8b732b5e1efb01>

Ary, Et Al. (2010) Introduction To Research In Education. Wadsworth: Cengage Learning. Merriam, S. B (2009). Qualitative Research A Guide To Design And Implementation.

Marwan, Ardi. (2015). Empowering English Through Project-Based Learning With Ict. The Turkish Online Journal Of Educational Technology. October 2015. Volume 14 Issue 4.

Larasati, Andyani. (2015). Improving Students' Writing Skills Project-Based Learning Technique At Grade Xi Of Sma N 2 Sleman In The Academis Year Of 2014/2015. Thesis, Sarjana Pendidikan Degree In English Language Education, Universitas Negeri Yogyakarta.

Farich, M. (2018). The Implementation Of Project-Based Learning In Teaching Writing Recount Text To The Tenth Grader. Thesis, Stkip Al Hikmah Surabaya

Barker, R. (2000). Literacy Connections. New York. A Catalog Record For This Book Is Available From The British Library.

Zaim, M. (2017). Implementing Scientific Approach To Teach English At Senior High School In Indonesia. Published By Canadian Center Of Science And Education. Asian Social Science; Vol. 13, No. 2; 2017

Irawan, R., C. (2017). Implementasi Model Pembelajaran Discovery Learning Guna Meningkatkan Keaktifan Belajar Dan Minat Baca Siswa Kelas X Teknik Kendaraan Ringan Smk Negeri 1 Sedayu. Universitas Negeri Yogyakarta.

Saefuddin, A. & Berdiati, I. (2014). Pembelajaran Efektif. Bandung: Pt Remaja Rosdakarya.

Ramadhan, R. (2015). Students' And Teachers' Attitudes Towards Teachers' Corrective Feedback In Teaching Writing English As A Foreign Language (A Case Study At Surabaya State University Of The Fifth Semester Students In Academic Year 2014/2015). Sebelas Maret University Surakarta

Halim, A. (2016). Students' Response Towards The Use Of Video In Teaching Listening At The English Department Of Tarbiyah And Teachers Training Faculty At Antasari State Institute For Islamic Studies Banjarmasin. Antasari State Institute For Islamic Studies Banjarmasin 2016 A.D./1437 H

Abdul Jabar Permana, Et Al. (2017). Tujuan Belajar Dan Pembelajaran. Program Studi Pendidikan Teknologi Dan Informasi Sekolah Tinggi Keguruan Ilmu Dan Pendidikan (Stkip) Garut 2017. Www.Academia.Edu/35398769/Makalah_Tujuan_Belajar_Dan_Pembelajaran_Pdf

Angela Dinasih W. C. (2019). Saintific Approach In 21st Century Learning In Indonesian Language Learning Vocational School Of Pharmacy. International Journal Of Active Learning Terakreditasi Sinta 4 [Http://Journal.Unnes.Ac.Id/Nju/Index.Php/ljal](http://Journal.Unnes.Ac.Id/Nju/Index.Php/ljal).

Syah. 2004. Psikologi Pendidikan Dengan Pendekatan Baru. Bandung: Pt Remaja Rosdakarya
[Http://Edutaka.Blogspot.Co.Id/2015/03/Model-Pembelajaran-Discoverylearning.Html](http://Edutaka.Blogspot.Co.Id/2015/03/Model-Pembelajaran-Discoverylearning.Html)

In'am. A. 2016 Learning Geometrythrough Discovery Learning Using A Scientific Approach. International Journal Of Instruction. File:///C:/Users/Hirate/Downloads/Learning_Geometry_Through_Discovery_Learning_Using.Pdf